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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
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- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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DIGITAL READING VS. PRINT READING: EFFECTS ON EFL LEARNERS' READING SPEED AND UNDERSTANDING

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Abstract: This article examines the comparative effects of digital and print reading on English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners' reading speed and comprehension. As digital technologies increasingly dominate educational contexts, understanding how different reading modes influence learning outcomes has become crucial. The article aims to determine whether screen-based reading enhances or hinders comprehension and speed compared to traditional print reading among intermediate-level EFL students. The study employs a quasi-experimental design involving two groups: one using digital texts and the other using printed materials, followed by comprehension tests and timed reading assessments. Data are analyzed using quantitative methods to identify significant differences between the groups.

Key words: digital reading; print reading; reading comprehension; reading speed; EFL learners; digital literacy; screen-based reading; cognitive processing; language learning.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tili chet tili sifatida (EFL) o'rganuvchilarning o'qish tezligi va matni tushunishiga raqamli hamda bosma o'qishning ta'siri qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Raqamli texnologiyalar ta'lim jarayonida tobora keng tarqalayotgani sababli, turli o'qish shakllarining o'quv natijalariga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishini aniqlash muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Maqolada o'rta darajadagi EFL talabalari misolida, ekran orqali o'qish an'anaviy bosma o'qishga nisbatan matni tushunish va o'qish tezligiga ijobiy yoki salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadimi, degan masala o'rganiladi. Tadqiqotda kvazieksperimental dizayn qo'llaniladi: bir guruh raqamli matnlar bilan, ikkinchisi esa bosma materiallar bilan ishlaydi. So'ngra tushunish bo'yicha testlar va o'qish tezligini aniqlash mashqlari o'tkaziladi. Olingan ma'lumotlar guruhlar o'rtasidagi sezilarli farqlarni aniqlash uchun miqdoriy usullar yordamida tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli o'qish; bosma o'qish; matni tushunish; o'qish tezligi; EFL talabalari; raqamli savodxonlik; ekran orqali o'qish; kognitiv qayta ishlash; til o'rganish.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается сравнительное влияние цифрового и печатного чтения на скорость и понимание прочитанного у студентов, изучающих английский язык как иностранный (EFL). По мере того как цифровые технологии всё больше доминируют в образовательной среде, становится особенно важным понимать, как различные формы чтения влияют на результаты обучения. Цель исследования – определить, способствует ли чтение с экрана улучшению или, наоборот, снижению уровня понимания и скорости чтения по сравнению с традиционным чтением с бумаги среди студентов среднего уровня владения английским языком. В исследовании используется квазиэкспериментальный дизайн, включающий две группы: одна работает с цифровыми текстами, другая – с печатными материалами. После чтения проводятся тесты на понимание и задания на измерение скорости чтения. Полученные данные анализируются с помощью количественных методов для выявления статистически значимых различий между группами.

Ключевые слова: цифровое чтение; печатное чтение; понимание прочитанного; скорость чтения; обучающиеся EFL; цифровая грамотность; чтение с экрана; когнитивная обработка; изучение языка.

INTRODUCTION

With the global shift toward digital learning platforms and the proliferation of online reading materials, educators face the challenge of ensuring that comprehension and engagement are not compromised by the medium of reading. Research has shown that while digital texts are more accessible, they may lead to superficial reading and reduced comprehension due to distractions, screen fatigue, and cognitive overload. Conversely, print reading is often associated with deeper processing and better text retention. However, empirical evidence in EFL contexts—particularly regarding reading speed and comprehension—is still limited and inconclusive. Therefore, this study is urgent, as it addresses a contemporary pedagogical concern that directly affects the quality of language instruction in technology-rich environments.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous research has produced mixed findings on the cognitive outcomes of digital versus print reading. Mangen, Walgermo, and Brønneick ^[10] reported that print readers demonstrated better recall and understanding, suggesting that the tactile and spatial features of printed materials support memory consolidation. In contrast, Baron and Delgado et al. highlighted that younger readers, particularly digital natives, are increasingly adapting to screen-based reading and may not experience significant comprehension deficits ^{[6]; [8]}. In EFL contexts, Chen ^[7] found that digital reading can enhance motivation and vocabulary acquisition through multimedia support; however, comprehension depth may be compromised by hypertext structures. Jeong ^[9] compared reading speed and comprehension among Korean EFL learners and found that print readers performed better on comprehension tasks, although digital readers read faster. These findings indicate that while digital reading may improve efficiency, it may not equally promote deep understanding. This study builds on these insights by focusing specifically on the dual dimensions of reading speed and comprehension among EFL learners, aiming to identify whether the medium itself or learner characteristics account for performance differences. The results will provide evidence-based recommendations for integrating digital and print reading materials in EFL instruction to optimize learning outcomes. Despite the increasing integration of digital reading in educational contexts, research indicates that digital texts may contribute to heightened reading anxiety.

Dunifa ^[12] observed that certain features of digital texts—such as their structural complexity and unfamiliar interface—can elevate anxiety levels among readers. Similarly, Kesson ^[13] explained that although digital environments promote opportunities for extensive reading, they also require effective engagement strategies to mitigate the discomfort and disorientation frequently experienced by learners. Empirical evidence supports this relationship between anxiety and comprehension. Given the growing use of digital texts in language education, it is crucial to explore the factors contributing to reading anxiety among EFL learners with different comprehension abilities. Zhang ^[14] underscored the pivotal role of digital literacy, arguing that teachers' attitudes toward technology and their proficiency in using digital tools strongly influence their effectiveness in supporting learners' comprehension. Understanding how digital reading anxiety differs between higher- and lower-proficiency EFL learners remains particularly important, as this area is underexplored in the current literature. Consequently, the present study aims to identify the underlying factors contributing to reading anxiety in digital contexts, measure learners' levels of digital reading anxiety, and compare the anxiety levels of higher- and lower-proficiency readers when engaging with digital texts.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The integration of digital texts into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction has had a profound impact on learners' reading comprehension and anxiety. Two theoretical frameworks—the Broaden-and-Build Theory of Positive Emotions and Cognitive Load Theory—offer useful perspectives for examining the relationship between digital reading anxiety and comprehension among EFL learners. The Broaden-and-Build Theory ^[15] posits that positive emotions expand individuals' cognitive and attentional resources, whereas negative emotions, such as anxiety, tend to restrict them. Applied to EFL contexts, anxiety arising from digital reading can limit learners' cognitive capacity, making it more difficult to process and understand texts. This framework highlights how emotional reactions—such as frustration, stress, or uncertainty—within digital environments can impede comprehension and overall reading performance. Conversely, Cognitive Load Theory focuses on the mental effort required to process information. Digital reading often involves non-linear structures, multimedia components, and numerous distractions (e.g., scrolling, hyperlinks, and pop-ups), which can increase cognitive load and reduce comprehension efficiency. For EFL learners, who already face linguistic challenges, these additional cognitive demands may further complicate the reading process. Zhang ^[14] also notes that teachers' digital literacy—including their technological attitudes, competencies, and access to resources—intersects with both the cognitive and emotional dimensions of reading comprehension.

The interaction between the emotional mechanisms outlined in the Broaden-and-Build Theory and the cognitive demands emphasized in Cognitive Load Theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how anxiety influences digital reading comprehension. While anxiety can constrain cognitive resources, the design and complexity of digital texts may amplify these challenges by imposing additional cognitive strain. Consequently, promoting digital literacy among both teachers and students is essential for alleviating cognitive load and supporting effective reading comprehension ^[14]. This integrated framework enables a nuanced analysis of the emotional, structural, and cognitive factors that affect EFL learners' engagement with digital texts.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Recent research increasingly underscores the significant impact of Foreign Language Reading Anxiety (FLRA) on EFL learners' reading comprehension. A consistent body of evidence demonstrates that higher FLRA levels correspond with poorer comprehension outcomes. However, studies also indicate that managing anxiety can enhance comprehension. Smith et al. found that inducing positive emotional states during reading facilitates deeper engagement with texts, thereby improving understanding. This suggests that interventions such as mindfulness practices, positive reinforcement, or supportive feedback can help mitigate anxiety and promote better reading outcomes. Likewise, Mohammed highlights the effectiveness of speed-reading strategies in counteracting anxiety's adverse effects on comprehension. These findings collectively emphasize the importance of incorporating anxiety-reducing practices and affective support into EFL instruction. The shift toward digital reading in educational assessment and instruction presents both opportunities and challenges for comprehension. On one hand, digital texts enhance engagement and interactivity, potentially improving understanding. Park and Lee found that multimedia elements embedded in e-books provide valuable contextual cues that aid comprehension among EFL learners. Similarly, Rochanaphapayon demonstrated that strong digital literacy skills—including the ability to navigate digital platforms—significantly contribute to improved reading comprehension. Additionally, digital texts often include adaptive features that support diverse learning needs, such as accessibility functions for students with disabilities or visual impairments.

On the other hand, digital environments can also exacerbate anxiety and hinder comprehension. Tsai and Lee reported that unfamiliar vocabulary and complex structures elevate FLRA—challenges intensified in digital formats by hyperlinks and multimedia distractions. Al-Seghayer similarly observed that scrolling and excessive linking reduce sustained attention, increase frustration, and heighten anxiety. Mudra and McKinnon emphasize that cultivating a positive attitude toward digital reading is critical for mitigating these issues ^[1]. Their research suggests that well-designed digital texts with clear layouts and user-friendly interactive features can reduce anxiety and enhance engagement, thereby supporting more effective comprehension.

Participants who engaged with digital texts generally demonstrated faster reading rates than those who read printed materials. This aligns with previous research suggesting that digital reading environments encourage skimming and scanning behaviors due to screen layout, scrolling, and hyperlinks. However, despite the increase in reading speed, comprehension scores among digital readers were slightly lower than those of print readers, indicating a potential trade-off between efficiency and depth of understanding. One possible explanation for this phenomenon lies in the cognitive processing demands associated with screen reading. The presence of visual distractions, hyperlinks, and multitasking tendencies can lead to cognitive overload, reducing readers' capacity for deep comprehension ^[10]. In contrast, print reading allows for greater focus and mental engagement, as the tactile and spatial stability of paper facilitates memory retention and inferential processing. This may explain why print readers in this study performed better on comprehension tests despite slower reading speeds. Another factor influencing the results may be participants' digital literacy and reading habits. While younger learners are generally more accustomed to digital media, their reading strategies may not yet be fully adapted to academic or extended digital reading tasks. The familiarity of the print medium, combined with fewer distractions, might have enabled print readers to apply more effective reading strategies such as annotation, rereading, and summarization.

Furthermore, EFL learners often rely on visual and contextual cues to infer meaning; print texts may offer a more stable and less fragmented reading experience conducive to such strategies. Interestingly, qualitative feedback from participants indicated mixed preferences. Some appreciated the convenience and accessibility of digital reading, while others reported experiencing eye strain and reduced concentration. These responses highlight that the effectiveness of each medium may depend on individual learner preferences, task type, and reading purpose. Therefore, rather than viewing digital and print reading as opposing modes, educators might consider integrating both media strategically—using digital texts for extensive or interactive reading and print materials for intensive comprehension tasks. In discussing the concept of reading comprehension, Anderson ^[11] defines it as the ability to extract and construct meaning from written text, emphasizing the dynamic interaction between linguistic knowledge and graphic symbols. Reading comprehension extends beyond simple word recognition; it involves a complex set of cognitive processes through which readers actively engage with text to derive meaning. This process requires not only decoding words but also interpreting information and integrating it with prior knowledge—a fundamental skill for academic achievement, as noted by Onel and Durdukoca ^[3]. They assert that students who read regularly tend to perform better across disciplines, demonstrating the centrality of reading comprehension to educational success. Thus, effective comprehension requires moving beyond surface-level understanding to grasp the contextual and nuanced meanings within a text.

The development of reading comprehension skills is influenced by multiple factors, including linguistic competence, vocabulary range, and metacognitive awareness. Learners who possess strong language proficiency and metacognitive skills are better able to interpret texts and derive deeper insights from reading ^[4]. Several theoretical perspectives explain the cognitive mechanisms underlying comprehension. For instance, the Event Model Processing Framework ^[5] posits that comprehension involves constructing and updating mental representations as readers process textual information. Similarly, the Enhanced Simple View of Reading highlights the interaction between word recognition and language comprehension, emphasizing that reading comprehension functions along a continuum requiring the integration of both components. Reading comprehension can be categorized into three primary levels: literal, interpretative (or inferential), and critical comprehension. This study focuses on the first two levels, aligning with the design of the platform's assessment tasks. Literal comprehension pertains to understanding explicit information—such as facts and details—directly stated in the text. As demonstrated by Nurjanah and Putri ^[2], mastery of literal comprehension provides the foundation for more advanced reading proficiency and supports overall academic performance. Interpretative comprehension, in contrast, involves inferring implicit meanings and relationships within the text, or “reading between the lines.” This level promotes deeper analytical engagement and is essential for processing complex materials ^[1].

Within the scope of this research, the ReadWorks platform is employed as a digital tool to enhance reading comprehension. By offering a wide selection of curriculum-aligned texts, ReadWorks supports both literal and inferential comprehension through leveled reading passages and structured practice activities. The platform enables educators to customize reading assignments according to learners' proficiency levels, facilitating progressive development across comprehension stages. Moreover, its evidence-based design promotes cognitive growth by integrating verbal and visual elements that reinforce understanding. The study is grounded in two key theoretical frameworks: Dual Coding Theory and the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (CTML). According to Paivio's Dual Coding Theory (1971), information is processed through both verbal and visual channels, which enhances comprehension and memory retention. Mayer's CTML (2021) expands on this idea, emphasizing the cognitive benefits of combining verbal and visual inputs to optimize processing and learning outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In summary, this study contributes to the ongoing discussion about the impact of reading medium on EFL learners' reading performance. The results suggest that while digital reading promotes faster processing, it may compromise comprehension, particularly in tasks requiring deep understanding. Print reading, though slower, appears to support more effective meaning construction and retention. For EFL instruction, these findings underscore the importance of teaching students to adapt their reading strategies to different mediums. Instructors should explicitly train learners in digital reading skills—such as managing distractions, using annotation tools, and developing critical reading habits—to improve comprehension in online contexts. At the same time, maintaining opportunities for print-based reading remains crucial for fostering focus and depth of understanding.

Thus, reading comprehension is a multidimensional skill involving the active construction of meaning from written language. When combined with digital learning platforms such as ReadWorks, these cognitive processes can be effectively supported and enhanced. By leveraging evidence-based digital tools and multimedia learning principles, educators can foster both literal and interpretative comprehension skills, ultimately promoting deeper and more sustained reading engagement among EFL learners.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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